

IMPROVEMENT OF LOSSLESS TEXT COMPRESSION METHODS USING A HYBRID METHOD BY THE INTEGRATION OF RLE, LZW AND HUFFMAN CODING ALGORITHMS

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ABSTRACT

In the field of computer science, data compression is essential in the process of data transfer because it reduces file size without losing information. Issues that depend on the characteristics of the text can greatly affect the effectiveness of any compression algorithm. Consequently, each traditional compression algorithm has its own strengths and limitations. Therefore, a highly efficient compression method that achieves higher compression ratio is needed. In this paper, based on the sequential implementation of Huffman, RLE and LZW algorithms, a hybrid data compression method has been proposed. The algorithms have been individually evaluated and compared in terms of compression ratio and compressed file size. We conclude that in terms of compression ratio and compressed file size, LZW is better than Huffman and RLE. The results show that the proposed hybrid algorithm achieves the highest average compression ratio is 2.42 and the lowest average compressed file size is 1138.5 or less compared to the individual implementations of the algorithms. Thus, it can be concluded that the proposed hybrid method enhances lossless text compression in terms of compression ratio and file size according to compression metrics.

KEYWORDS

DATA COMPRESSION, LOSSLESS COMPRESSION, RUN LENGTH CODING (RLE), HUFFMAN CODING, LEMPEL-ZIV-WELCH (LZW).

1. INTRODUCTION

With development of communication systems, large amounts of data have been created [1]. In the field of computer science, one major technique for the reduction of the size of data files without loss of their essential information is data compression. It was necessary to find a way to reduce the volume of data, hence the urgent need for data compression. In order to ensure the minimum use of storage space and bandwidth when transferring files over communication channels, data compression techniques are used that aim to reduce the size of files [2]. As a result, the number of errors that can occur during the file transfer process is reduced. This helps to manage data efficiently and enables a faster and more efficient way of communicating between devices and systems [3]. Data compression is the critical method. Whether it is for multi-media or transmission purposes, data requires to store in a compressed form to minimize the cost of storage and transportation. There are numerous data compression methods that can be used to achieve high compression ratios, as specified by the application [4]. Data compression is classified into two basic classes of data compression mechanisms are lossy data compression

methods employed to compact images, video and audio files, and lossless data compression methods employed to compress binary files for transmission or storage [5]. Various compression techniques are available which are used for applications in different types of formats such as text, image, video, sound etc. [6]. Dictionary based coding and statistical based techniques are used for text compression [7]. For data compression in text format, Huffman coding and Lempel-Ziv-Welch (LZW), Run Length Coding (RLE) algorithms are considered to be highly efficient [8]. Some of the techniques used for image or video compression are Discrete Cosine Transformation (DCT), Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), Joint Photographic Expert Group (JPEG) [9].

This paper focuses on three fundamental lossless text compression algorithms. The efficient text compression algorithms are RLE, LZW, and Huffman Coding which were used to decrease the file or text size without losing any original data. RLE algorithm is effective for compressing simple text or image data with many repetitive elements by replacing consecutive repeated characters with a single character and a count [10]. The LZW encoding algorithm creates a dynamic dictionary of repeated substrings and replaces them with shorter symbols. Therefore, it is one of the basic methods for data compression, as it is highly efficient in compressing texts with repeated patterns. Although it depends on the characteristics of the data [11]. Huffman encoding algorithm creates a binary tree on the basis of the frequency of the symbols, and assigns shorter codes to the symbols that occur most frequently [12].

Data compression is critical for optimizing the storage and transmission of text data, especially in bandwidth- and storage-limited environments [13]. A critical issue addressed in the literature is that the effectiveness of any of the compression algorithms RLE, LZW and Huffman can be significantly affected by issues that depend on text characteristics (e.g., text redundancy, distribution of character frequencies and occurrence of repetitive patterns). As a result, traditional compression algorithms such as RLE, LZW and Huffman coding each have unique strengths and limitations [14], [15]. Therefore, the objectives of this paper are as follows: (1) to review the literature on RLE, LZW and Huffman compression methods and how they work, (2) to propose a method that integrates RLE, LZW and Huffman compression algorithms into a hybrid compression method based on sequential execution to improve the overall compression performance and achieve optimal compression results. Finally, (3) To evaluate the performance of these algorithms separately on text files and compare them with the proposed hybrid method in terms of compressed file size and compression ratio.

The rest of the paper has the following structure: Related work on text compression methods is reviewed in section 2. In section 3, the proposed methodology is presented, with details on the RLE, Huffman and LZW algorithms. Section 4 presents the results obtained and analyzed. Finally, Section 5 concludes of this paper.

2. RELATED WORKS

The current literature on data compression methods reviewed in this section. It focused on the data compression algorithms namely RLE, and LZW Huffman coding. This paper highlights the strengths and weaknesses for algorithms by discussion on related studies. Furthermore, we discuss studies that have proposed hybrid approaches that combine different compression algorithms to improve the efficiency of data compression. A simple compression algorithm is the run-length encoding (RLE) algorithm, which is an effective compression algorithm for processing image compression and text files containing repetitive data. However, its weakness is that the size of the output data can be larger than the size of the input data. Therefore, future researches should rely on hybrid methods for data compression. Due to the combination of traditional compression methods advantages. Thus, hybrid methods will be more adaptive than traditional methods [16]. On the other hand, Huffman coding is a popular method for lossless

data compression. Since, it generates variable length codes where the code length depends on the redundancy of characters. In this context, many studies have been discussed about applying the Huffman algorithm or comparing it with other data compression methods [17]. Besides, many studies have paid great attention to LZW algorithm due to its dynamic dictionary-based approach and its flexibility in application to different file types. Therefore, researchers resorted to comparing its performance with other data compression algorithms [18]. From the literature, Kadhim et al. [19] presented a performance comparison study between LZW and adaptive Huffman and used four different text files to evaluate the test. They used evaluation metrics as compression time, decompression time, and bit rate. They concluded that the adaptive Huffman algorithm was better in terms of file compression and bitrate. In contrast, LZW algorithm was faster in decompressing files. Gopinath and Ravisankar [20] presented compression study among RLE, Huffman, and LZW methods. It based on required execution time, compression ratio, storage rate, and space savings. They concluded that LZW was the best in terms a compression ratio of 4:1 and space saving of 76.9% compared to other techniques. The study by Mohammadi et al. [21], proposed a hybrid lossless compression technique. It combined Huffman coding and LZW algorithm. Their results showed no degradation in image quality after decompression. Also, hybrid method achieved compression ratio of 37.85%. Hossain and Rahman [22] offered a comparative study for RLE, Huffman and LZW algorithms. They concluded that LZW algorithm was the best in terms of compression ratio, file decompression size and space saving. However, Huffman coding is the best in term compression time. Tariq et al. [23] proposed an approach that combines two lossless compression techniques, Huffman and LZ4. They conclude that the proposed approach significantly reduced text file size, achieving average savings between 73.649% and 79.708%. As a result, it can have a positive impact on the reliability and efficiency of electronic communication systems. Liu et al. [24] have proposed a lossless compression algorithm to improve the compression ratio of the image. The proposed algorithm combines linear prediction and integer wavelet transform with output coefficient processing and Huffman coding. The experiment results show that the compression ratio was improved by at least 6.22 % up to 72.36 %. They concluded that the proposed algorithm is more suitable to compress images with complex structure and high resolution. In the current years, there has been a growing interest in hybrid compression techniques that combine the strengths of algorithms, often using two compression algorithms as presented in related works. Therefore, this paper aims to focus on a hybrid compression method based on three effective algorithms. It leads to improve and increase the compression ratio. In addition, to balance the advantages of each of the compression algorithms used to create a different hybrid method that achieves new insights in the field of data compression, using a sequential implementation of RLE, LZW and Huffman algorithms.

3. PROPOSED METHOD

Basically, the proposed method in this paper is a combination of lossless data compression techniques, namely RLE, and LZW Huffman coding. The sequential implementation of algorithms is the main principle of the proposed hybrid method. Using the specified compression algorithms consecutively to compress a number of texts files in such a manner as to achieve the compression in successive stages. Thus, the main objective of exploiting the strengths of each algorithm to reduce the data size is achieved. The proposed method is divided into a compression system and a decompression system consisting of several stages, as shown in the figure1.

Figure 1: The proposed method.

Figure 1 illustrates the proposed method relies on compressing the text file in three successive stages, first encoding with the RLE algorithm, then the LZW algorithm and finally the Huffman algorithm to obtain the compressed file. On the other hand, it works on decompressing in three other stages in reverse, starting with decompressing using the Huffman algorithm, then the LZW algorithm, and finally the RLE algorithm as follows:

3.1. The RLE Algorithm

Run Length Algorithm (RLE) is a simple and popular method of compressing data. It is very effective for data that has strings of characters with repetitions. This algorithm encodes a repeated string of characters as a pair of symbols. The pair has two parts, the first part is the length of the string and the second part is the character to be encoded. The compressed file size by the RLE algorithm can be larger than the original file. To solve this problem, the Huffman algorithm can be used after RLE to encode each pair separately [25]. The pseudocode of the RLE encoding algorithm as shown in Algorithm 1 and the pseudocode of the RLE decoding algorithm as shown in Algorithm 2 are shown as follows:

Algorithm 1: FUNCTION RLE_Encode(input_data)

```

encoded_data = ""
index = 0
WHILE index < LENGTH(input_data)
    symbol = input_data[index]
    count = 1
    WHILE (index + 1) < LENGTH(input_data) AND input_data[index] == input_data[index + 1]
        count = count + 1
        index = index + 1
    encoded_data = encoded_data + symbol + TO_STRING(count)
    index = index + 1
RETURN encoded_data

```

Algorithm 2: FUNCTION RLE_Decode(compressed_data)

```

decoded_data = ""
index = 0
WHILE index < LENGTH(compressed_data)
    symbol = compressed_data[index]
    index = index + 1
    count = ""
    WHILE index < LENGTH(compressed_data) AND IS_DIGIT(compressed_data[index])
        count = count + compressed_data[index]
        index = index + 1
    count = INTEGER(count)
    decoded_data = decoded_data + (symbol * count)
RETURN decoded_data

```

3.2. The LZW algorithm

The LZW algorithm is an efficient lossless compression method for text files that contain redundancy patterns. The encoding algorithm generates dynamic dictionary that contain code for each the recurring pattern. The first step of the encoding algorithm is to insert each ASCII character into a table and then assign a code between 0 and 255 to each character. For each new entry, if the table does not contain the character or pattern, that entry is inserted. The efficiency of the algorithm increases with the increase in the number of strings that contain recurring patterns. However, it faces challenges related to dictionary inflation. Also, its weakness is its failure to adapt to dynamic changes in the data [27]. The pseudocode of the LZW encoding algorithm as shown in Algorithm 3 and the pseudocode of the LZW decoding algorithm as shown in Algorithm 4 are shown as follows:

Algorithm 3: FUNCTION LZW_Encode(input_data):

```

dictionary = {}
FOR i = 0 TO 255:
    dictionary[CHAR(i)] = i

current_string = ""
encoded_data = []
next_code = 256
FOR symbol IN input_data
    new_string = current_string + symbol
    IF new_string IN dictionary:
        current_string = new_string
    ELSE
        encoded_data.APPEND(dictionary[current_string])
        dictionary[new_string] = next_code
        next_code = next_code + 1
        current_string = symbol

IF current_string != "":
    encoded_data.APPEND(dictionary[current_string])
RETURN encoded_data

```

Algorithm 4: FUNCTION LZW_Decode(encoded_data):

```

dictionary = {}
FOR i = 0 TO 255:
    dictionary[i] = CHAR(i)
current_code = encoded_data[0]
current_string = dictionary[current_code]
decoded_data = current_string
next_code = 256
FOR i = 1 TO LENGTH(encoded_data) - 1:
    next_code_value = encoded_data[i]
    IF next_code_value IN dictionary:
        entry = dictionary[next_code_value]
    ELSE:
        entry = current_string + current_string[0]
    decoded_data = decoded_data + entry
    dictionary[next_code] = current_string + entry[0]
    next_code = next_code + 1
    current_string = entry
RETURN decoded_data

```

3.3. The Huffman algorithm

Huffman algorithm is an efficient algorithm used for lossless data compression. It relies on generating codes consisting of zeros and ones with variable character lengths. The length of the character determines how often that character occurs in the input stream. The algorithm assigns the smallest code to the most frequently occurring character, while the largest code is assigned to the least frequently occurring character. Because the codes are constructed in such a way that no code assigned to a character is a prefix to any other character, the Huffman algorithm has the advantage of guaranteeing accurate decoding of the resulting code sequence. For this reason, it is considered to be an effective method for lossless data compression, although it has the disadvantages of not being able to adapt to variable data and of high time complexity [26]. The pseudocode of the Huffman encoding algorithm as shown in Algorithm 5 and the pseudocode of the Huffman decoding algorithm as shown in Algorithm 6 are shown as follows:

Algorithm 5: FUNCTION Huffman_Encode(input_data)

```

// Step 1: Calculate the frequency of each symbol in the input data
frequency_table = CALCULATE_FREQUENCY(input_data)
// Step 2: Build the Huffman tree based on the frequency table
huffman_tree = BUILD_HUFFMAN_TREE(frequency_table)
// Step 3: Generate the Huffman codes for each symbol
huffman_codes = GENERATE_CODES(huffman_tree)
// Step 4: Encode the input data using the generated Huffman codes
encoded_data = ""
FOR symbol IN input_data:
    encoded_data = encoded_data + huffman_codes[symbol]
// Return the encoded data and the Huffman tree (needed for decoding)
RETURN encoded_data, huffman_tree

```

Algorithm 6: FUNCTION Huffman_Decode(encoded_data, huffman_tree)

```

decoded_data = ""
current_node = huffman_tree
FOR bit IN encoded_data:
    IF bit == '0':
        current_node = current_node.left
    ELSE:
        current_node = current_node.right
    IF current_node is a leaf:
        decoded_data = decoded_data + current_node.symbol
        current_node = huffman_tree
RETURN decoded_data

```

3.4. The Hybrid Method

The proposed hybrid method is based on the sequential implementation of RLE, LZW and Huffman coding, where the specified compression methods are executed sequentially, compressing the text file in consecutive steps, i.e. compression with the RLE algorithm, then the resulting compressed file is compressed with the LZW algorithm, and finally the resulting compressed file is compressed with the Huffman coding algorithm. As for the decompression method, it is done in reverse, first decompressing with the Huffman coding, then with the LZW algorithm and finally with the RLE algorithm to obtain the original file without losing any data. The pseudocode of the hybrid encoding algorithm as shown in Algorithm 7 and the pseudocode of the hybrid decoding algorithm as shown in Algorithm 8 are shown as follows:

Algorithm 7: FUNCTION Hybrid_Encode(input_data)

```

// Step 1: Apply Run-Length Encoding (RLE)
rle_encoded_data = RLE_Encode(input_data)
// Step 2: Apply LZW Encoding on the RLE encoded data
lzw_encoded_data = LZW_Encode(rle_encoded_data)
// Step 3: Apply Huffman Encoding on the LZW encoded data
huffman_encoded_data, huffman_tree = Huffman_Encode(lzw_encoded_data)
// Return the fully encoded data and the Huffman tree (needed for decoding)
RETURN huffman_encoded_data, huffman_tree

```

Algorithm 8: FUNCTION Hybrid_Decode(encoded_data, huffman_tree)

```

// Step 1: Apply Huffman Decoding using the Huffman tree
huffman_decoded_data = Huffman_Decode(encoded_data, huffman_tree)
// Step 2: Apply LZW Decoding on the Huffman decoded data
lzw_decoded_data = LZW_Decode(huffman_decoded_data)
// Step 3: Apply Run-Length Decoding (RLE)
rle_decoded_data = RLE_Decode(lzw_decoded_data)
// Return the fully decoded data
RETURN rle_decoded_data

```

In order to evaluate the performance of the RLE, LZW and Huffman compression algorithms and then to compare them with the proposed hybrid method in terms of the compressed file size and the compression ratio. Using Python 3.6 as the programming language, the algorithms used were applied separately to text files by generating code for the above algorithms. Ten different sized text files were selected, and the test was conducted to obtain the data. For each encoding method and for the hybrid method, the original file size and the compressed file size were observed. In addition, the compression ratio was calculated for each compression method in use and for the hybrid method in accordance with the following [28]:

Compression Ratio (CR)= (BC / AC) (1)

BC =file size before compression.

AC = file size after compression.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, the experimental results are presented and discussed. Based on the compression ratio and the size of the compressed file, a comparative evaluation of RLE, LZW and Huffman data compression methods against the proposed method is performed. These metrics are highlighted for comparison of the test results of the four algorithms above. In this context these metrics are very important. The compression ratio is calculated using Eq. (1) as shown in Table1.

Table1: Comparative evaluation of data compression algorithms.

Text file name	BC / KB	RLE		LZW		Huffman		Hybrid Method	
		AC	CR	AC	CR	AC	CR	AC	CR
text1	55	32	1.72	24	2.29	29	1.90	22	2.50
text2	164	87	1.89	80	2.05	83	1.98	71	2.31
text3	283	158	1.79	132	2.14	151	1.87	104	2.72
text4	417	221	1.89	203	2.05	211	1.98	181	2.30
text5	678	387	1.75	312	2.17	378	1.79	258	2.63
text6	845	473	1.79	402	2.10	458	1.84	389	2.17
text7	1188	631	1.88	532	2.23	612	1.94	514	2.31
text8	3153	1677	1.88	1456	2.17	1662	1.90	1231	2.56
text9	6563	3312	1.98	3112	2.11	3412	1.92	2738	2.40
text10	13462	7517	1.79	7043	1.91	7311	1.84	5877	2.29
average	2680.8	1449.5	1.84	1329.6	2.12	1430.7	1.90	1138.5	2.42

Based on the results in Table 1, and by testing each compression method separately, the average compression ratios and compressed file sizes were calculated. The results showed that the RLE algorithm reduced all files by an average of 1449.5 from their original size, regardless of the variation in file size. The average compression ratio was greater than 1.84. The compression ratio was lower or higher depending on the characteristics of some cases that depend on the repetition ratio in the file. The results showed that the Huffman coding algorithm reduced the files size after compression by an average of 1430.7 compared to their original size. It did not affect by the difference in file sizes. Therefore, the average of file size reduction achieved by the Huffman algorithm was lower than the RLE algorithm. The average compression ratio was higher than 1.90. In some cases, the compression ratio was lower, or it was higher in others. Besides, the compression ratio of the Huffman algorithm was higher than the RLE algorithm. This indicates that the Huffman algorithm is better than RLE in terms of compression ratio and file size after compression. According to the results obtained, the LZW algorithm achieved average of 1329.6 in terms of file size after compression. And, the average compression ratio was more than 2.12. In some cases, it was higher or lower. It can be concluded, LZW algorithm is better than the Huffman and RLE algorithms. Because, the LZW algorithm achieved the highest compression ratio and the lowest file size reduction rate after compression.

Figure 2: Comparison of data compression algorithms based on compression ratio.

The Figure 2 indicates that the proposed hybrid method has a high performance for compressing the data. The compression ratio has increased for all the compressed files and has achieved a compression ratio of 2.42 or higher on an average basis. This indicates that compared to the compression ratio of RLE, LZW and Huffman algorithms individually, the hybrid method achieved the best compression ratio.

Figure 3: Comparison of data compression algorithms based on the size of the compressed file.

Figure 3 shows that the proposed hybrid method gives high performance. The result of file size after compression decreased for each compressed file. The average file size was 1138.5 or less. This indicates that the hybrid method achieved the lowest compressed file size compared to RLE, LZW and Huffman algorithms individually.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper is concerned with a major issue, that of lossless compression methods for text data. Three main data compression methods namely RLE, LZW and Huffman have been studied. In this paper, we have proposed a hybrid data compression method based on the sequential

implementation of the mentioned algorithms. The performance of data compression algorithms was compared based on the compression ratio values and the compressed file size. Previous studies have confirmed the importance of these measures in order to determine the efficiency of the algorithms. According to the results obtained, we concluded that the LZW algorithm is better than Huffman and RLE in terms of compression ratio and compressed file size. The results showed that the proposed hybrid method achieved the highest average compression ratio, which was 2.42 or higher. In addition, it achieved the lowest average compressed file size, which was 1138.5 or less. Therefore, it can be concluded that the proposed hybrid method is more efficient than the compression algorithms. Consequently, the proposed hybrid method can be improves the lossless text compression methods.

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